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Application of Marine Spatial Planning tools for tidal stream farm micro-siting

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Abstract

The operation of tidal stream energy farms may interfere with other uses of the marine space, especially in depth-limited areas (estuaries, rivers, etc.) which are typically subject to multiple demands of use. The Marine Spatial Planning Directive (MSP) was passed by the European Commission in 2014 to ensure a harmonic coexistence between different maritime activities and to protect the marine environment. In this context, the objective of this work is to present a methodology based on MSP tools for tidal-farm siting in depth-limited areas. The methodology is illustrated through a case study: Ria de Ribadeo, a shallow-water estuary in NW Spain. Having considered a number of uses (archaeological, biodiversity, fishing, aquaculture, recreational and navigation), two exploitable tidal farm sites (Areas A and C) with annual energy densities of 1 GWhm^{-2} were found. The estuary is periodically dredged to maintain navigation. Dredging-related risks were analysed using a novel indicator, the Dredging Associated Risk (DAR), based on which Area C was discarded and Area A had its exploitable surface area reduced by 25%. In sum, the methodology proposed was proven to be effective for tidal stream farm planning.

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9 *Keywords:* Depth-limited tidal sites, Good Environmental Status (GES),
10 Maritime Planning System, Dredging Associated Risk (DAR), Ria de Ribadeo
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13 1. Introduction

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16 With the aim of mitigating climate change and reducing fossil fuel dependence,
17 from the beginning of the 21st century, different policies have been developed,
18 initiating a transition towards a non-polluting and sustainable energy model. Ex-
19 amples of those policies are: (i) the Paris Agreement (United Nations) [1], (ii) the
20 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations) [2] and (iii) the EU
21 2030 Framework for Climate and Energy (European Union) [3]. The latter aims to
22 increase the share of renewables up to 32% of the EU's energy consumption and,
23 cutting Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions by 40% compared to 1990 levels [4]. In
24 this context, Marine Renewable Energy (MRE), which presents an abundant and
25 geographically-diverse resource (up to 32 TW) [5], is expected to play an impor-
26 tant role to achieve the aforementioned goals. For this purpose, in 2015 the EU
27 Commission created the Ocean Energy Forum, with the objective of developing
28 strategic road-maps for the development of a MRE industry. Consequently, a year
29 later, the road-map *Building ocean energy for Europe* was released [6], identifying
30 that: (i) MRE could supply up to 10% of EU's energy demand by 2050, (ii) di-
31 versification of the EU's low-carbon generation capacity is required to achieve the
32 goals in terms of GHG emissions; (iii) MRE exploitation may reduce significantly
33 GHG emissions (up to 276 Mt CO₂e annually) by 2050, and (iv) MRE represents
34 a fantastic opportunity to develop a new industrial sector, boosting EU's economy
35 and contributing to the long-term sustainability of its coastal regions.

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37 Within the large variety of MRE sources, tidal stream energy, with an estimated
38 global resource of 120 GW [7], stands out. Tidal stream energy is characteristic
39 of coastal regions, where tidal height variations combine with the morphological
40 conditions, to produce tidal currents [8]. Consequently, the kinetic energy stored
41 in the tidal currents is used for electricity generation, by means of Tidal Energy
42 Converters (TECs), which are placed directly into the flow [9]. In this context,
43 the main advantages of tidal stream energy are: (i) renewable nature and high
44 predictability of the resource [10] (ii) high load factors associated to tidal currents
45 [11] and (iii) non-existence of extreme flows that could jeopardise the long-term
46 survivability of submerged TECs (i.e. tidal streams velocities rarely exceed 6 m s⁻¹)
47 [11]. Despite all these facts, tidal stream energy is far from being commercially
48 viable for large-scale electricity generation [12]. On these grounds, the following
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9 facts stand out: (i) despite recent breakthroughs (MeyGen tidal energy project
10 [13]), TEC technology is not yet mature, (ii) few locations around the world meet
11 the requirements in terms of tidal flow velocities ($> 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and water depths (> 25
12 m) for the operation of the first and second generation of TEC concepts [14], (iii)
13 TEC operation usually takes place in harsh marine environments, which increases
14 significantly the difficulty and costs of installation and maintenance operations
15 [12], (iv) operation of TECs may cause significant disruptions of different marine
16 environmental processes such as transient and residual circulation patterns [15],
17 transport of suspended matter (e.g. pollutants [16], nutrients [17] and sediments
18 [18]) and ambient turbulence conditions [19], and last but not least (v) potential
19 interactions with other marine uses such as navigation [20], fishing, aquaculture
20 [21] and recreational activities [22].
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24 The latter highlights the necessity of managing the different maritime uses
25 and activities (MRE, fishing, aquaculture, recreational and others) using a holistic
26 approach. For this purpose, in 2014 the EU released the 2014/89/EU Directive on
27 Maritime Spatial Planning (MSPD) [23], whose main objectives are: (i) reduce
28 conflicts and create synergies between different maritime uses [24], (ii) set a
29 clear and predictable legal framework to attract investments in maritime activities
30 [25, 26], (iii) increase cross-border cooperation between EU Member States [27]
31 and (iv) ensure the protection of the marine environment by identifying impacts and
32 opportunities for multiple maritime uses. Consequently, EU Member States had
33 to transpose Directive 2014/89/EU into their national law by 2016 and define their
34 respective Maritime Spatial Plans (MSPs) by 2021. Regarding MRE exploitation,
35 MSPD offers the opportunity to improve and harmonise the legal framework for
36 licensing MRE projects, increase legal security for MRE stakeholders and, reduce
37 and arbitrate conflicts with other maritime users [28].
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41 For the specific case of Spain, Royal Decree 363/2017 [29] transposes Directive
42 2014/89/EU into the Spanish national law. RD 363/2017, in its general provisions
43 and article 10, includes the exploitation of MRE within the different maritime
44 uses to be considered for the elaboration of future MSPs. For each of the Spanish
45 marine demarcations, MSPs are still under development (currently in the public
46 consultation stage) and they are expected to come into force by the end of 2021 or
47 early 2022. MSPs will follow a hybrid planning approach with the aim of ensuring
48 a seamless coexistence between maritime uses and activities, while ensuring a
49 Good Environmental Status (GES). For this purpose, MSPs identify the so-called
50 *priority use areas*, for which a set of rules and provisions are defined to avoid
51 that the main use of the area is not compromised by other marine activities. In
52 consequence, proposals for other marine activities must demonstrate compatibility
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9 with the priority use of the marine area. On these grounds, planning the installation
10 of tidal farms will require a detailed (i) spatial identification of different maritime
11 uses and (ii) assessment of the potential impacts caused by other marine activities
12 on the operating conditions of tidal farms, and *vice versa*; with the purpose of
13 ensuring an harmonic coexistence among the different maritime uses of the area
14 of interest. As a result, Marine Spatial Planning will contribute to decrease
15 the level of uncertainty of tidal energy projects, decreasing interactions with other
16 marine activities and enhancing legal certainty [28]. Further details on the Spanish
17 maritime legislation can be found in Section 2.

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21 The technological development of TECs, has brought the opportunity of ex-
22 ploiting the tidal stream energy resource in a wider variety of coastal locations,
23 especially at shallow tidally-driven estuaries and rivers [30], which also host of
24 multitude of marine uses (shipping, fishing, aquaculture and recreational activ-
25 ities). Moreover, the tidal stream resource at depth-limited regions is highly
26 sensitive to natural (sediment transport) and/or anthropogenic (dredging of navi-
27 gation channels) bathymetric changes [31]. Consequently, the holistic approach
28 of Marine Spatial Planning appears as an excellent tool for tidal farm siting, es-
29 pecially in those regions. Previous research has dealt in detail with the optimum
30 siting of tidal stream energy farms, considering different constraints such as avail-
31 able resource [14], maintenance [32], operating costs [33], power production [34],
32 layout optimisation [35], environmental impact [36] and economic viability [37];
33 however, few works have applied Marine Spatial Planning in depth to find the
34 optimum location for tidal farms [38, 39, 40].

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38 Against the foregoing backdrop, the objective of this paper is to present a
39 methodology based on Marine Spatial Planning with the aim of finding the most
40 suitable location for the installation of tidal farms in depth-limited regions, using
41 for this purpose Ria de Ribadeo (Figure 1), a shallow and highly energetic estuary
42 located in NW Spain [41], as case study. The remainder of this paper is structured as
43 follows: Section 2 presents the main characteristics of the Spanish legal framework
44 for maritime activities. Section 3 describes in the detail the maritime uses and
45 characteristics of Ria de Ribadeo. Section 4 presents the Dredging Associated Risk
46 (DAR) indicator for depth-limited tidal sites. Section 5 illustrates the application
47 of Marine Spatial Planning for tidal farm siting in Ria de Ribadeo. Finally,
48 conclusions are drawn in Section 6.
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9 **2. Spanish Maritime Legal Framework**

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11 Spain, as any other EU Member State, legislates the protection of marine en-
12 vironment and management of maritime activities, according to: (i) Directive
13 92/43/EEC on nature conservation [42], (ii) Marine Strategy Framework Di-
14 rective 2008/56/EC (MSFD) [43] and (iii) Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
15 2014/89/EU (MSPD) [23].
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18 In May 1992, the European Council approved Directive 92/43/EEC on the
19 conservation of natural habitats and wild fauna and flora, establishing the EU
20 Natura 2000 ecological network of protected areas (Sites of Community Impor-
21 tance, SICs), preserving them against potentially damaging developments. EU
22 Commission Decisions 2004/813/EC [44] and 2006/613/EC [45] define the SICs
23 for the Atlantic and Mediterranean biogeographical regions of Spain, respectively.
24 In this context, Law 42/2007 [46], which transposes Directive 92/43/EEC into
25 the Spanish domestic law, establishes in its article 42.3 that Spanish autonomous
26 regions have a period of six years to declare the SICs, which belong to their ju-
27 risdiction area, as Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) and/or Special Protection
28 Areas for Birds (SPAB) and to elaborate managing and monitoring plans for those
29 areas.
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33 In June 2008, the European Parliament approved the Marine Strategy Frame-
34 work Directive 2008/56/EC (MSFD) [43], which aims to preserve the marine
35 environment and to ensure its long-term sustainable use. MSFD was transposed
36 into the Spanish national law in December 2010, by means of Law 41/2010 [47],
37 whose main goal is to achieve GES in the marine environment. To this end, spe-
38 cific strategies for each Spanish marine demarcation were developed, proposing
39 coherent planning of activities and uses of the marine environment compatible
40 with the preservation of its biodiversity. Marine strategies are subject to be re-
41 visited every six years. In addition, Law 41/2010 creates the Network of Marine
42 Protected Areas (NMPAs), setting the mechanisms for their designation, preserva-
43 tion, environmental monitoring and management of marine activities. Examples
44 of MPAs are areas belonging to Natura 2000 network (SICs, SPAs and SPABs),
45 World Heritage and Biosphere Reserve UNESCO areas [48] and Ramsar [49] and
46 OSPAR [50] sites.
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49 RD 363/2017 [29], of April 2017 transposes Maritime Spatial Planning Direc-
50 tive 2014/89/EU (MSPD) into the Spanish law, establishing the legal framework
51 for the management of marine spaces. For this purpose, RD 363/2017 contem-
52 plates the elaboration of Marine Spatial Plans (MSPs) for each of the Spanish
53 marine demarcations, with the aim of ensuring a sustainable development and
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harmonic coexistence of marine sectors and protection of the marine environment. For this purpose, RD 363/2017 establishes the guidelines for the elaboration and revision of MSPs. However, it does not establish either priority criteria for the execution of maritime activities or rules to arbitrate conflicts between different maritime users [28]. Regarding the exploitation of Marine Renewable Energy (MRE), RD 363/2017 highlights in Article 5.c the need of producing energy from MRE sources to foment a sustainable development of coastal regions, while Article 10.2 includes MRE exploitation among the maritime activities to be considered for the elaboration of MSPs. As aforementioned, MSPs, which are currently under public consultation, are expected to come into force by the end of 2021 or early 2022, and will be susceptible to revision, every ten years. Overall, MSPs will follow a hybrid planning approach, prioritising the coexistence of multiple marine activities in the same marine space, as well as ensuring its GES. Nonetheless, *priority use areas* will be defined and, therefore, proposals for other marine activities must demonstrate compatibility with the designated use of the area. It is worth noting that protected marine areas are classified by the MSPs as priority use areas for the preservation of biodiversity and will be regulated according to the legislation applicable to them. Finally, *high-potential areas* will be also identified, giving priority to uses and activities, which present a high-future development [51].

Additionally, RD 1028/2007 [52] regulates the licensing process of MRE installations in the Spanish jurisdictional waters. RD 1028/2007 contemplates the commercial licensing only for off-shore wind farms, while for other types of MRE it establishes a simplified licensing procedure for experimental installations. RD 1028/2007 also classifies the Spanish littoral in appropriate and non-appropriate areas for the installation of off-shore wind farms, based on an environmental impact assessment carried out by the inter-ministerial commission of Marine Environment, Industry and Tourism. On these grounds, it is expected that MRE exploitation areas proposed by RD 1028/2007 will be overruled by future MSPs [53]. Furthermore, future regulatory changes are expected to streamline licensing procedures of MRE plants [53, 54]. Finally, Figure 2 shows the linkages among the different legislation presented in this section.

3. Characterisation of maritime exclusive areas for Ria de Ribadeo

Ria de Ribadeo is a shallow coastal embayment, with a total surface area of approximately 10 km^2 , located in NW Spain (Figure 1). Its location, naturally sheltered from the harsh marine environment of the Bay of Biscay, has prompted

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9 a significant development of different maritime uses such as aquaculture, tourism
10 and recreational activities. Ria de Ribadeo also acts as a natural border between
11 the autonomous regions of Galicia and Asturias (Figure 1), housing a multitude
12 of commercial and trading activities throughout the ports of Ribadeo and Figueras
13 (Figure 1). In addition, Ria de Ribadeo presents remarkable biodiversity and
14 archaeological heritage [49]. Finally, Ria de Ribadeo has an abundant tidal stream
15 energy resource [41], with three potential tidal sites identified at the middle *ria*
16 [31], whose exploitation could bring a fantastic opportunity for the development
17 of a new industrial sector in the region.
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20 However, the exploitation of the tidal resource could interfere with the partic-
21 ular marine environment [56] and biodiversity of the *ria* [57] and with other
22 relevant socio-economic activities such as aquaculture and marine navigation [58].
23 Moreover, periodic dredging operations of the approach channels of Ports of Rib-
24 adeo and Figueras alter the hydrodynamic patterns of the *ria* [31]. Consequently,
25 the available resource and operating conditions of tidal farms could be drasti-
26 cally modified, jeopardising their long-term viability [31]. In this context, before
27 planning the installation of a tidal farm in Ria de Ribadeo a holistic approach is
28 necessary, considering the potential interactions of tidal farm operation with the
29 maritime uses of the *ria*, which are described in detail from Sections 3.1 to 3.6,
30 using for their definition, GIS spatial analysis (Figures 3 to 5).
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33 34 35 36 *3.1. Special Areas of Conservation (SAC) and Special Protection Areas for Birds* 37 *(SPAB)*

38 Decision 2004/813/EC identified Ria de Ribadeo as a Site of Community Impor-
39 tance (SIC) within the Atlantic biogeographical region [59]. As mentioned in
40 Section 2, Law 42/2007 establishes that the Spanish autonomous regions should
41 classify SICs, lying inside their jurisdiction areas, as SACs and/or SPABs. There-
42 fore, the parliament of Galicia approved Decree 37/2014 [60], which identified 59
43 SACs and 16 SPABs, and also proposes managing and monitoring plans for those
44 areas. In this context, Ria de Ribadeo was classified as SPAB (ref. ES0000085
45 [61]), and as SAC (ref. ES11200002 [60]) within the estuary/wetland category. As
46 a result, Ria de Ribadeo is included in the Spanish Network of Marine Protected
47 Areas (NMPAs) [62]. Decree 37/2014 classifies both SACs and SPABs into three
48 different categories: (i) protected areas, in which only traditional activities with
49 little to no impact on ecosystems are allowed, (ii) conservation areas, where tradi-
50 tional and non-traditional activities compatible with the local ecosystems could be
51 carried out and (iii) general use areas, in which industrial activities may be allowed
52 after a detailed environmental impact assessment.
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Figure 3 shows the spatial distribution of the aforementioned areas across Ria de Ribadeo. It can be observed that in the mouth of River Eo, there is a protected area, which covers a surface of 160 *ha*. The inner and outer sections of the *ria* are marked as conservation areas, spanning a total surface of 392 *ha*. Conversely, the middle section of the *ria* (80 *ha*) is declared as a general use area. Furthermore, it is worth noting, that RD 363/2017 and, consequently, MSPD applies only for the outer section of the *ria*, since their inner and middle sections lie in the category of transitional waters (Figure 3). In this context, the draft version of the MSP for the North-Atlantic Spanish demarcation classifies the outer section of Ria de Ribadeo as a priority use area for the preservation of biodiversity [55], highlighting Decree 37/2014 as the applicable legislation to manage maritime activities. All in all, and despite the inner and middle sections of the *Ria de Ribadeo* lie outside the scope of RD 363/2017, the tools provided by MSP are still very valuable to find the optimum location of tidal farms in the area of study.

3.2. *Archaeological protected sites*

Ria de Ribadeo presents an outstanding archaeological heritage. A multitude of archaeological remains, from centuries XVI to XVIII belonging to merchant and war ships, have been found in the outer and middle sections of the *ria* (Figure 4). Considering the large number of documented shipwrecks in the *ria*, further archaeological wrecks are expected to remain undiscovered, especially in the surroundings of the marina harbour, which coincides with the historical location of the port. Table 1 summarises the main characteristics and archaeological value of the wrecks found in the *ria*.

In this context, Law 5/2016 [63], which regulates the cultural heritage of the autonomous region of Galicia, establishes protection areas of 200 *m* radius for archaeological sites, where any seabed action is prohibited. Figure 4 shows the different archaeological protected areas of Ribadeo, which are mainly concentrated around the marina harbour with two additional areas located at both sides of the *ria* mouth, spanning a total surface 32.64 *ha* (Table 2). Consequently, the installation of tidal farms in those areas is discarded beforehand, since its operation could disrupt seabed morphology, jeopardising the integrity of archaeological wrecks.

3.3. *Biodiversity protected sites*

Ria de Ribadeo behaves as a positive, partially mixed estuary with a two-layer estuarine circulation pattern [64], which derives from the complex interaction of tides, fresh water run-offs and wind conditions. In addition, from the months of April to October, Ria de Ribadeo experiences coastal upwelling events caused by

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10 northerly shelf winds. As a result, oceanic water (Eastern North Atlantic Central
11 Water), which is cold and nutrient-rich, enters the *ria* [65]. The combination of
12 those coastal processes explains the high biological productivity of Ria de Ribadeo
13 [66]. In this context, an abundant population of macro-algae species such as
14 *pelvetia canaliculata* and *ulva* is present in the inter-tidal areas of the middle section
15 of the *ria* (Figure 5). Additional algae species such as *ascophyllum nodosum*,
16 *fucus ceranoides*, *fucus espirabis*, *fucus vesiculosus*, *gracilaria verrucosa* and
17 *mastocarpus stellatus* can also be found in the *ria* [67]. Therefore, in order to
18 preserve this marine ecosystem, the macro-algae sites (Figure 5) are catalogued as
19 exclusion zones for other maritime activities, covering a surface of 290 *ha* (Table
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24 3.4. Fishing and aquaculture sites

25 As mentioned in the previous section, Ria de Ribadeo stands out for its marine
26 biodiversity, laying the foundation for a strong fishing and aquaculture industry.
27 On the one hand, the fishing grounds are mainly located in the *ria* mouth (Figure 5).
28 On the other hand, shell-fishing gathering (bivalve molluscs and octopuses) repre-
29 sents an important maritime activity both in the middle and inner sections of the
30 *ria* (Figure 3). Finally, in recent years, the farming of oysters on floating-wooden
31 platforms is increasing significantly, requiring a significant amount of space, es-
32 pecially at the inner *ria* (Figure 5). Again, in order to avoid potential disruptions
33 to fishing and aquaculture activities, the aforementioned sites are excluded from
34 additional marine uses.
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39 3.5. Touristic sites

40 Touristic and recreational activities are an important source of employment and
41 income generation for the region. In this context, Law 2/2013, which regulates
42 the protection and sustainable use of coastal areas, establishes in its article 69 that
43 bathing or beach areas should cover at least a strip of 200 *m* width parallel to the
44 coast, in which any other activity is prohibited for safety reasons. For the rest of
45 the coast, an exclusive public domain area of 50 *m* width is defined. Finally, Figure
46 5 shows the spatial distribution of public domain and beach areas in the *ria*, which
47 span 155 *ha* and 31.3 *ha*, respectively.
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52 3.6. Marine navigation areas

53 The privileged location of Ria de Ribadeo (Figure 1) makes ports of Figueras
54 and, especially, Ribadeo relevant trading ports at a regional level. Consequently,
55 ensuring adequate operating conditions for both ports becomes essential. For this
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9 purpose, any disruption in the approach channels of both ports must be avoided.
10 The main navigation channel of the *ria* is located on its left side (Figure 5), with
11 a total width of 90 *m* and a draught of 5 *m* relative to the Lowest Astronomical
12 Tide (LAT). A branch of the main channel, whose main dimensions are 50 *m* wide
13 and 3 *m* draught, gives access to the port of Figueras (Figure 5). As a result, both
14 channels cover a total surface of 28.4 *ha*.
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17 However, the complex circulation pattern present in the *ria* [64], drives a
18 significant sediment transport towards its middle section, causing significant sed-
19 imentation in the approach channels of Ribadeo and Figueras ports. To ensure
20 operativity of both ports, maintenance-dredging operations are required every 3.5
21 years [58]. As result the magnitude and direction of tidal currents will experiment
22 significant and repetitive variations over long time horizons. The latter confirms
23 the need of accounting for the effects of dredging operations, when planning the
24 installation of tidal farms in depth-limited regions, like Ria de Ribadeo [31].
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27 28 **4. Dredging Associated Risk (DAR) indicator for depth-limited coastal areas** 29

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31 As mentioned in previous sections, tidal currents characteristic of shallow coastal
32 regions are highly sensitive to natural and/or anthropogenic bathymetric changes.
33 Among them, periodic dredging operations of marine navigation channels stand
34 out. As a result, the magnitude and direction of tidal currents may be significantly
35 altered, jeopardising the long term technical and economic viability of tidal farms
36 located in depth-limited regions [31]. On these grounds, a novel risk indicator,
37 Dredging Associated Risk (DAR), was developed *ad hoc*, with the aim of quan-
38 tifying the uncertainty derived from dredging operations. DAR represents the
39 fraction of time for a specific location, in which the relative difference between
40 the magnitude of tidal currents for the pre- and post-dredging scenarios, is higher
41 than an uncertainty threshold value (e.g. 10 %, 20 % and 30 %). Consequently,
42 DAR ranges from zero (no risk) to one (maximum risk). DAR does not discrim-
43 inate between increments and decrements of flow velocities, since both of them
44 are considered equally harmful. For instance, a decrease of tidal flow velocities
45 (after dredging), would result in significantly less power production and lower
46 incomes for developers and investors. Conversely, significant increment of flow
47 velocities (after dredging), could cause scour problems of bottom anchors and
48 higher pressure loads on TEC structural elements, jeopardising the operating life
49 of TECs. Lastly, when computing DAR, time-series of flow data (for the pre-
50 and post-dredging scenarios) should cover a period of at least one year, with a
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9 minimum frequency of three hours, to account for the seasonal variations of the
10 tidal-stream currents.

11 For the present study, pre- and post-dredging flow conditions were determined
12 by means of the Delft3D-Flow hydrodynamic model [68]. For this purpose, two
13 numerical models were set-up considering the bathymetric datasets corresponding
14 with pre- and post-dredging scenarios, respectively. The simulations covered an
15 average year, using as model inputs, time-series of mean monthly values of river
16 discharges, wind magnitude and direction, salinity and temperature at the ocean
17 boundaries. For further details, the readers are referred to Ref. [31], in which an
18 exhaustive description of the model implementation and validation is presented.
19 Consequently, DAR was computed based on annual hourly flow data, at each cell
20 of the numerical hydrodynamic grid, which allows obtaining a spatial distribution
21 of DAR for Ria de Ribadeo. Figure 6 presents the algorithm used to compute DAR.
22 Finally, it is worth mentioning that DAR methodology can be applied elsewhere,
23 considering also different values for the uncertainty thresholds.
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29 **5. Tidal farm siting for Ria de Ribadeo**

30 *5.1. Ria de Ribadeo: Resource characterisation*

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32 When considering the installation of tidal farms at Ria de Ribadeo, among the
33 constraints presented in Section 3, the following stand out: (i) TEC operation must
34 be respectful with the seabed, to preserve its archaeological heritage and (ii) TECs
35 must meet the water depth limitations (approx. 4 m at LAT), present in the most
36 energetic locations of the *ria*. Consequently, floating TECs appear as the most
37 appropriate technology since, they are considerably less disruptive for the seabed
38 than bottom-fixed TECs. In this context, the horizontal-axis, floating Evopod
39 turbine, was used as reference for the identification of potential tidal farm sites.
40 Table 3 summarises the main technical characteristics of the Evopod Turbine.
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45 Based on the annual flow conditions of Ria de Ribadeo, computed by the
46 hydrodynamic model presented in Section 4, the operativity of the Evopod turbine
47 was analysed. For this purpose, the number of annual hours, for which flow
48 velocity exceeds the *cut-in* of the turbine (Table 3), were determined. Figure 7
49 shows the results obtained. As can be observed, only the middle section of the
50 *ria* presents adequate operational conditions for the Evopod turbine, with some
51 areas easily exceeding 2200 operating hours per year. On these grounds, a detailed
52 characterisation of the tidal stream resource was carried out for the middle section
53 of the *ria*. For this purpose, the tidal resource was assessed on an annual basis,
54 in contrast to the traditional approach, which is only based on the flow conditions
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9 of representative tidal cycles (e.g. spring-neap tidal cycle). Figure 8 shows the
10 spatial distribution of annual energy density. As can be observed, areas A, B
11 and C stand out in terms of tidal stream resource. Area A, with a total surface
12 of 22 *ha* and annual energy densities in the order of 0.9 GWhm^{-2} , is the less
13 energetic of the three, due to the blockage effect caused by the piles of the bridge
14 that crosses the estuary. Area B, which covers a surface of 8.1 *ha*, presents also a
15 larger tidal stream resource, with annual energy densities up to 1 GWhm^{-2} . Area
16 C appears as the most suitable location from the energetic point of view, with an
17 annual resource of 1.2 GWhm^{-2} , spanning a total surface of 10.9 *ha*. Finally, it is
18 important to point out, that the results presented in Figures 7 and 8 are based on
19 the pre-dredging flow conditions, which represents the most plausible scenario in
20 the *ria*.
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25 5.2. *Ria de Ribadeo: Dredging Associated Risk (DAR)*

26 With the purpose of quantifying the uncertainties derived from dredging opera-
27 tions, DAR was computed for Ria de Ribadeo following the algorithm presented in
28 Figure 6 (Section 4). For this study, three different uncertainty levels (i.e. relative
29 differences of flow velocities between pre- and post-dredging scenarios) of 10, 20
30 and 30 % were considered to illustrate the behaviour of DAR indicator. The results
31 obtained confirm the necessity of including the effects of dredging in the decision-
32 making process, when planning the installation of tidal farms in Ria de Ribadeo.
33 As expected, DAR increases as the required level of uncertainty for the operating
34 flow conditions decreases. For a level of uncertainty of 10%, DAR exceeds values
35 of 0.8 (i.e. high risk) at the middle section of the *ria* (Figure 9.a), where the most
36 energetic areas (A, B and C) are located (Section 5.1). Figure 9.b shows the DAR
37 values for a level of uncertainty of 20%. In this case, DAR decreases considerably
38 for the regions of interest (Areas A, B and C), with its maximum values up to 0.5
39 (i.e. mid risk). For an uncertainty threshold of 30%, DAR decreases dramatically
40 across the *ria*, barely exceeding values of 0.2 (i.e. low risk) for Areas A, B and
41 C (Figure 9.c). In consequence, the selection of uncertainty levels, which will
42 depend mainly on the periodicity and extent of dredging operations and the risk
43 aversion of developers and investors of tidal farm projects, play a significant role
44 in DAR outputs. For instance, regions with frequent dredging operations during
45 the useful life of the tidal farm (eg. every 4 or 5 years) should adopt a conser-
46 vative uncertainty level of 10%. Conversely, for regions with a lower periodicity
47 of dredging operations (7 to 10 years), higher uncertainty levels (20 or 30%) can
48 be adopted. Regardless of the uncertainty level selected, it is recommended that
49 regions with values exceeding 0.2 should be discarded for tidal farm operation
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9 since, for at least 20% of annual hours (1752 *h*) relative differences between pre-
10 and post-dredging flow velocities exceed the uncertainty level selected (e.g. 10%).
11 As result, tidal farms could present either lower power production (due to flow
12 velocity reductions) or withstand harsher flow conditions (due to flow velocity
13 increments), jeopardising their long-term economic or technical feasibility, re-
14 spectively. In sum, DAR gives the opportunity to map tidal farm sites, identifying
15 the regions with higher dredging-related risks, which may be very helpful for the
16 decision-making of tidal farm projects, especially at depth-limited regions, which
17 are normally subjected to periodic changes of bathymetric conditions.
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21 5.3. *Ria de Ribadeo: Tidal-stream sites*

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23 Following the exclusionary approach of the maritime legal framework applicable to
24 Ria de Ribadeo (Sections 2 and 3.1), GIS mapping was used for the identification of
25 potential tidal farm sites across the *ria*. For this purpose, geographical information
26 of maritime exclusive areas (Section 3), tidal stream resource (Section 5.1), DAR
27 spatial distribution (Section 5.2) and water depth limitations (Section 5.1), was
28 combined. Figure 10 presents the results obtained. Maritime exclusive areas
29 (60.6% of *ria* surface), highlighted in grey in Figure 10, are discarded for tidal
30 farm operation, according to RD 1028/2007 (Section 2). In addition, water depth
31 requirements of Evopod turbines (Table 2), limit their operation to water depths of
32 at least 4 *m*. Consequently, only East sectors of Areas A and C can be considered
33 appropriate for tidal farm operation (marked as Level II areas in Figure 10). Among
34 them, Area A appears as the most suitable location for locating a tidal farm, with an
35 annual energy density exceeding 1 $GWhm^{-2}$ and a total surface of approximately
36 5.6 *ha*.
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41 Furthermore, Figure 11 presents the DAR distribution values for the tidal farm
42 sites previously identified (Areas A and C). Overall, as the requirements in terms
43 of level of uncertainty (i.e. relative differences of flow velocities between pre- and
44 post-dredging scenarios) are softened, the usable surface of tidal sites increases.
45 For a level of uncertainty of 10% (Figure 11.a), most part of Area C presents DAR
46 values exceeding 0.8 (i.e. after dredging magnitude of tidal currents vary more
47 than 10% at least for 80% of annual hours) and, therefore, should be discarded
48 for tidal farm operation. Conversely, Northern sectors of Area A (Figure 11.a),
49 which span a total surface area of 42.3 *ha* and with annual energy densities of 0.5
50 $GWhm^{-2}$, are suitable for tidal stream exploitation since, DAR presents values
51 lower than 0.2. Raising the level of uncertainty up to 20% (Figure 11.b), translates
52 into a surface increment of 0.58 *ha* in Area A, mainly concentrated in its southern
53 sector. Finally, assuming higher levels of uncertainty (e.g. 30%), the majority of
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9 Areas A and C become available for the installation of tidal farms (Figure 11.c).
10 According to the high periodicity of dredging operations (every 3.5 years) and their
11 significant impacts on the flow conditions of Areas A and C, the results obtained
12 for the most restrictive DAR uncertainty level (10%) should be retained for the
13 implementation of tidal farms. Finally, Table 4 summarises the usable surface of
14 Areas A and C for the different DAR uncertainty levels considered.
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18 **6. Conclusions**

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20 In 2014 the European Commission released Directive 2014/89/EU on Maritime
21 Spatial Planning, whose main goals are to ensure a harmonic coexistence among
22 different maritime activities and to protect the marine environment. Regarding
23 MRE exploitation, Directive 2014/89/EU offers the opportunity to improve and
24 harmonise the legal framework for licensing MRE projects, increase legal security
25 for MRE stakeholders and reduce/arbitrate conflicts with other maritime users.
26 For the specific case of Spain, Directive 2014/89/EU was transposed by means of
27 RD 363/2017, which identifies MRE as a relevant activity to be considered for the
28 elaboration of future Maritime Spatial Plans (MSPs). According to previous ma-
29 rine legislation (RD 1028/2007), MSPs are expected to present a zoning approach,
30 consisting of maritime exclusive areas. In this context, the objective of the present
31 work is to present a methodology using Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) tools, to
32 locate tidal stream energy farms at depth-limited regions. For this purpose, Ria de
33 Ribadeo (NW Spain) a shallow coastal embayment, with a substantial tidal stream
34 energy resource, was used as case study.
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40 In general terms, the application of MSP tools for tidal farm siting appears to
41 perform well for the present case study, identifying appropriate locations for tidal
42 farm operation, avoiding potential conflicts with other maritime activities (fishing,
43 aquaculture, navigation and recreational) and preserving biological and archaeo-
44 logical heritages of Ria de Ribadeo. After the identification of maritime exclusive
45 areas only two exploitable tidal farm sites (Areas A and C), with values of annual
46 energy density up to 1 GWhm^{-2} , were found. However, potential disruptions on
47 tidal farm operating conditions, derived from other maritime activities, must be
48 also included as part of MSP. In the case of Ria de Ribadeo, periodic dredging
49 of navigation channels may impact significantly the tidal currents of Areas A and
50 C, which translates into high levels of uncertainty in terms of power production.
51 In this context, a site-specific risk indicator, Dredging Associated Risk (DAR),
52 was developed *ad hoc*. DAR ranges from zero (no risk) to one (maximum risk),
53 representing the fraction of annual hours, in which relative differences between
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9 pre- and post-dredging flow velocities, exceed an uncertainty threshold percentage.
10 For the tidal farm sites identified, DAR exceeds values of 0.8 (high risk), high-
11 lighting the importance of accounting for the disruptions caused by other maritime
12 activities, in this case dredging operations, when planning the installation of tidal
13 farms using MSP tools. Based on the results obtained, the authors recommended
14 that areas with DAR values exceeding 0.2 (i.e. after dredging tidal flow velocities
15 vary more than the uncertainty threshold defined by DAR users, for at least 20%
16 of annual hours) should be discarded for tidal farm operation. According to this
17 criterium, the exploitable surface for tidal sites A and C, decreases 25% and 98%,
18 respectively. It is important to note, that DAR can be applied elsewhere, using
19 different values of threshold uncertainty levels. Finally, the recommended DAR
20 limit to discard tidal farms sites must be considered as a first indication and should
21 be corroborated by further research at different locations.
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26 In summary, this paper presents a MSP-based methodology for tidal farm
27 siting, accounting for the risks associated to anthropogenic bathymetric changes,
28 which are especially relevant for depth-limited regions. Nonetheless, additional
29 constraints relevant for tidal farm siting, such as distances to grid connection points,
30 seabed geology and socio-economic aspects are not considered in this work and
31 will be dealt with as a continuation of this research.
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36
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Figure Captions

Figure 1: Location of Ria de Ribadeo.

Figure 2: Linkages between Spanish maritime legislation.

Figure 3: Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), Special Protection Areas for Birds (SPABs) and North-Atlantic Marine Demarcation (NAMD) areas at Ria de Ribadeo.

Figure 4: Archaeological protected areas at Ria de Ribadeo.

Figure 5: GIS mapping of exclusive maritime zones at Ria de Ribadeo.

Figure 6: Algorithm for the calculation of Dredging Associated Risk (DAR) indicator

Figure 7: Spatial distribution of annual operating hours for the Evopod Turbine

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of annual energy density for Ria de Ribadeo

Figure 9: DAR spatial distribution for Ria de Ribadeo. (a) Uncertainty Level of 10%. (b) Uncertainty Level of 20%. (c) Uncertainty Level of 30%.

Figure 10: GIS mapping for tidal farm siting at Ria de Ribadeo

Figure 11: DAR levels for potential tidal sites at Ria de Ribadeo

Figure 1

Figure2

Figure3

Figure4

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure8

Figure9

Figure10

Figure11

	Description
<i>Pancha Island Cannon</i>	3 pieces of iron artillery
	12 iron cannons with ammunition
<i>Wreck Illán cove</i>	Valuable ceramic remains
	Remains of the hull of an unknown wreck.
<i>Unidentified wreck</i>	Unknown wreck of the 18 th century
<i>Lonely cannon</i>	Cannon belonging to an unknown wreck
<i>Anchor</i>	Anchor belonging to an undiscovered wreck
<i>Ship Galga Andaluza</i>	Spanish pirate ship
<i>Ship Corbeta San Francisco</i>	Spanish pirate ship
<i>Steamship Cabo Torres</i>	Merchant ship sunk in 1887
<i>Galeón Santiago de Galicia</i>	Ship of the Spanish Navy (XVI century). Considered the best preserved Spanish galleon

Table 1: Main characteristics of the archaeological remains found in Ria de Ribadeo

	Surface (ha)
Archaeological sites	32.64
Fishing and shell-fishing grounds	38.64
Aquaculture sites	30.77
Macro-Algae sites	289.55
Public domain areas	155.04
Beach areas	31.29
Navigation channels	28.43

Table 2: Surface of Maritime exclusive areas

Type	Floating
Diameter (<i>m</i>)	3
Cut-in velocity (ms^{-1})	0.7
Cut-off velocity (ms^{-1})	3.0
Rated velocity (ms^{-1})	1.9
Rated power (<i>kW</i>)	25

Table 3: Main technical characteristics of the Evopod Turbine

	Area A	Area B	Area C
Total Surface (<i>ha</i>)	22.2	8.2	10.9
Usable Surface (<i>ha</i>)	5.6	–	3.4
<i>DAR</i> _{10%} usable surface (<i>ha</i>)	4.3	–	0.06
<i>DAR</i> _{20%} usable surface (<i>ha</i>)	4.8	–	1.9
<i>DAR</i> _{30%} usable surface (<i>ha</i>)	4.9	–	3.4

Table 4: Surface of tidal sites A, B and C